
Research

Investigating linguistic sexism in teachers' talk at public university of Pakistan

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Abstract: Schools are regarded as the main socializing institutions. The language that the instructor uses has an impact on the pupils' overall personalities and self-perceptions. As a result, students' academic performance is jeopardized. This study focuses on the teachers' talk within classroom discourse and its effect on students' perceptions of themselves in Pakistani context. For this, 8 university students from social sciences were interviewed and 4 teachers were observed by classroom ethnography. During the study, data were gathered by audio-recording interviews and by observing student-teacher interactions in the classroom. By developing themes in thematic analysis and deductive coding, the findings from the qualitative method were acquired. The findings indicated that both male and female students feel excluded in the class because of the teachers' use of gendered language. They consequently take part in the class less, which negatively impacts their academic performance. The study also found that when teachers use sexist language in the classroom, it alters students' self-perceptions, which has an impact on them psychologically as well as academically and professionally. The promotion of gender norms as the reality of daily life by teachers' gender prejudices not only prevented pupils from succeeding academically but also made them oblivious to gender issues.

Keywords: Linguistic Sexism, gender discrimination, classroom discourse, gender norms, stereotypes

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Introduction

The term 'sexism' appears in the 1960s to indicate forms of discrimination against women (Wodak, 1997). Sexism is concealed in everyday conversation in a way that does not seem problematic. Most of the time, teachers speak insensitively without recognizing how their words may affect the students. Although linguistic sexism typically conveys bias against women, it can equally bare bias against men. Sexist language is a complete belief system that suggests one gender is superior or inferior to the other and does not just refer to a few words or phrases. For instance, stereotypes and jokes are one of a kind and are being used in a normalized way within classroom discourse by teachers. The use of gendered language is pervasive throughout society, institutions, and even families. It's crucial to consider

the context when deciding if a conversation is normal or sexist. For example, the sentence 'she is a good girl' when used for a girl who is 16 years old is not sexist. But if the same sentence is used for elderly women, it becomes sexist. It is clear that sexism is not present in individual language items but context is very important to understand the gendered language.

Sexism comes in two forms. One is benevolent sexism, which is positive (women are soft and delicate like flowers), and the other is negative (women look good in the kitchen). Additionally, sexism can be overt or covert. In both public and private settings, there are overt (e.g., chairman, used to refer to both men and women) and covert (jokes, analogies) kinds of linguistic discrimination against women. Sexism focus is given more on attitude or holding a belief not simply language use. Sexists are those who have beliefs regarding sex differences and the consequences those actions or practices have. (Frye 1981:9) and those actions or practices have consequences on one gender, not the other. (Shutte 1981:27) so sexism is concerned with those differences in males and females who have effects. The problem is, people do not recognize it as a problem at all because it is so institutionalized in schools. We do accept what we are being taught and said in process of learning. So, in the pedagogy, the practices should be revised and then implemented as non-sexist. Adamsky (1981) states that the few pronominal changes she made in her class led a great impact on female students in their self-esteem and confidence. So, changing sexist language might not have an impact on a bigger level i.e. society or social systems but such minor changes may impact both males and females. Conscious interpretation is very important in the formation of the process of meaning-making.

1.2 Sex role and subjectivity are problematic

Schools are considered to be primary socializing agents. Therefore, what is taught at school has an effect on the pupil. If there are gender biases, the student's subjectivity can be in danger. Be it a male or female. For quality education, schools should notice the amount of sexism that could affect males and females in their education qualifications, behaviors, career choices, life patterns, and so on. Classrooms with sexism can be attributed to many factors. The first and most important one is teacher's language and their behavior with the students in the class. Students' learning could heavily be affected by the language of an instructor. In one of the studies by Andrus, Jacobs, and Kuriloff (2018), it was noticed that female students do not get comments on their academic abilities the way they get on their physical appearance. Also, male students get more feedback than female students which impact negatively on them. Females are marginalized by primary authority in the classroom i.e., a teacher. This shows that teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the way gender is treated in the classroom. There's a need for self-making to eliminate sexism and gain quality education. The research's focus is on Feminist interventions which could be made integral to the process of personalization and can be set as a prominent pedagogic strategy.

Literature Review

Words cannot be judged individually without the context in which they are spoken. The meanings of words and chunks are always seen interconnected with society in which they are produced. Hodge & Kress (1988). Similarly, the spoken words have different connotations, phonemes, stresses which declare them as sexist moreover, the context of the said words is always given priority. For instance, saying 'you are such a baby' to a grown adult woman has a different connotation than saying this to an actual baby.

It is the language which shapes someone's personality and can act as a motivating force in how someone wanted to define themselves or liked to be defined. (Voloshinov 1973; Pecheux 1982). Brown & Leaper (2008) studied the experiences of young about sexism, evaluating the question 'what it is mean to be a girl'? Out of 600 females aged 12-18, 90% mentioned sexual harassment at least once. Such harsh comments can hurt their self-esteem. Not only their overall body image but also their attitudes towards others.

Language can be used to maintain the power and to manipulate people. Gender system determines social meanings about male and female and the sex roles within language. (Hodge & Kress 1988:98). Within set language parameters, the speaker assumes that she has a choice but without being aware she utters out what preexists in system and determines what can be stated. That means, the meaning lies so strongly other than the verbal one. There are internalized ideas of how a typical male or woman should behave in a society.

For example, milder expletives like 'oh dear!' for woman and strong swear words for a man. Here, gender is not only affecting the language competence but the beliefs and expectations of how we use the language. Researches has been done to sexist language which states that it has immense effects on short as well as long term on people's relations with one another and their own self-image. (Eberhardt 1976; Martyna 1980; Adamsky 1981)

Gender roles and norms:

O'Loughlin (2001) examines that gender is being produced and regulated in an EFL classroom. EFL classroom is an essential source for it (p.37). Butler state that through repeated performance of behaviors, our perception of masculinity and femininity is being created. (1988). In this way, gender is reconstructed again and again hence, is not static. There is no other way of creating a concept of gender other than us. We are responsible for creating the concept of gender through our constant actions.

Symbolic Interactional Approach

Gender is a part of everyday life. It is more about what a person acts and feels than something they are born with. In Kramer research, it was stated that women have to behave in a way that does not put their femininity as negative, there are speech notions which women and men have to follow respectively. Male speech is marked as louder, authoritarian, concise, and assertive whereas women's speech is friendlier and polite. Schur (1984) states, because of stigmatization of women, they face hindrances whether they are in workplace or classroom setting or it's getting a general success.

The three fundamental axioms of this theory help people to comprehend daily life events. Jeon, (2004). The basic level of symbolic Interactionism deals with the meanings that are subjective and are derived from the surroundings of people. It also considers that humans make sense of their surroundings and themselves through socialization. They are not born with this quality rather they learn it with their connections and encounters with different people. The last postulate of symbolic interactionism is about the culture that it has a significant impact on the construction of meaning. In some countries, nonverbal and vocal actions that are considered acceptable may not be acceptable rather considered offensive. Vejar, (2019).

From above mentioned principles it can be concluded that women's perceptions can be influenced heavily by the surroundings particularly in the classroom setting as they spend significant amount of time growing up there, dealing with world's perceptions on her as well as their own. This is because of consistent division of genders. Due to these gender expectations on male and female, it is possible to conclude that women have been taught to stick to gender distinctions (Fuchs Epstein, 1986). In relate to Symbolic Interactionism, George Herbert Mead (1934), developed three stages of self-discovery. The Play stage that is the first stage which involves a person who will identify all the important details of their life and replicate the behavior according to their understanding of social norms. The individual then enters the game stage, assuming the role they have witnessed in others who are similar to them. In the last stage, they believe that a person's behavior is greatly influenced by the expectation of other people's perceptions of them. Knowing that this "other" is observing them, a person is divided between their instinctive reaction and the response which is socially acceptable to any situation which they might think as true. (Vejar, 2019). This idea promotes widely accepted social norms, putting people into gendered boxes on the basis of preexisting assumptions of the gender identity that exists. The individuality can be seen with both individual and societal definitions that operate as symbols that humans absorb (Littlejohn, 1977).

Consequences of Gender Exclusive Language:

Fuchs Epstein, (1986) claimed that language is considered to reflect the society's control over women. The pronoun "he" is frequently identified as universal pronoun when looking back at the origin of the English language.

Noll, Lowry, and Bryant (2018) investigated the concept of gender-neutral pronouns, focusing "he" pronoun used universally is no longer appropriate to use for both the genders. They noticed the impact of using "he" versus "they" pronoun as gender neutral. The study was conducted 15 years apart. The participants were given sentences to read which includes "he", and "they", in both the experiments. Respondents were given a lexical decision to react to, as a means to demonstrate influence of pronouns and gendered nouns process. The findings back with the theory that pronoun "he" slowed down the processing of feminine nouns and "they" speeds up the process. The results showed that the use of pronoun "they" is more inclusive than the pronoun "he".

Adoption of Gender-Inclusive Language and students' perceptions about it:

Cheng and Ghajarieh (2009) investigated gender bias in the classroom using "teacher-to-student" and "student-to-student" conversations. Their report included examples of gender-biased classroom discourses and a list of recommendations for reducing the impact of gendered discourses in the classroom. This is supported by a recent survey by the National Education Union and UK Feminista (2017), which found that 66% of female students and 37% of male students in mixed-gender have seen or witnessed sexist language at school. Furthermore, at least once a week, 64% of teachers in mixed-gender secondary schools hear sexist language in the classroom. Other studies on this subject focused on learners' understanding of gender inclusive language and their perceptions of it. Kennedy (1993) conducted a survey of 348 students to assess their knowledge of inclusive language and discovered that the students had received very limited training and instruction in using non-sexist language. The students, on the other hand, were eager to learn about it because they believe that non-sexist language is vital.

Similarly, Jacobs et al. (1998) conducted a study of Singaporean students' attitudes on gender inclusive English and discovered that the language was seen favorably by the majority, which was reinforced by the students' work, which demonstrated the use of gender fair language. Bengoechea and Simon (2014) also conducted a poll of 500 university students to assess their attitudes toward specific Spanish non-sexist linguistic practices. Unlike the good results of the other studies, however, this revealed that a large majority of respondents were hesitant to accept dual gender. Furthermore, of the policies mentioned, the use of feminine terminology for professions received the most opposition. These statistics clearly demonstrate the public's opposition to the initiatives. The importance of understanding the linguistics community's attitudes toward language policies, according to Bengoechea (2011), "has a huge impact on the success or failure of language planning and policy." Apart from looking into students' perspectives on gender inclusive language, it is also necessary to look into instructors' perspectives, as they are one of the primary agents in the micro-level implementation of these policies, notably in schools and universities (Pauwels and Winter, 2006). "Teachers' style of thinking is vital, as they should apparently support language policies in class," Bengoechea (2011) added.

Jacobs et al. (1996) investigated Asian instructors' attitudes toward gender inclusive English, finding that the majority of participants utilized gender-exclusive materials in their classes but are willing to adopt gender inclusive English. A portion of Lomotey's (2017) research looked into whether teachers would be willing or accepting of utilizing anti-sexist language alternatives in their classrooms, and the majority of the respondents said yes.

Research Questions:

1. What are the gendered words used by teachers in classroom?
2. What are the perceptions of students about their identity?

Theoretical Framework:

For this study, Feminist Post Structuralist Discourse Analysis (FPDA) has been taken as a theoretical framework. It is an approach to analyze intertextualized discourse in spoken interaction. As it has post structuralist element, which deals with the principle of ambiguity, complexity diversity, recognition, connection, functionality and transformation. The theoretical framework is taken in consideration of gender differentiation to be the prominent aspect of the approach. Taking FPDA in consideration for marginalized voices in the class and giving them space. It is best suited for classroom discourse as it has some tendency to change their condition. The focus is not to polarize males and villains and females as victims as FPDA argues subject positions are to be complex and complicated. Subject positions fluctuate between matrix of powerlessness and powerfulness. This shift can happen across a range of different speech events, within a single speech context, or literally within a few moments of interaction. It can even happen simultaneously.

Research Methodology

Qualitative research design has been used for this study. The researcher believes that qualitative research will help her in providing in-depth knowledge of the subject. Qualitative researchers are interested in understanding the meaning people have constructed, that is, how people make sense of their world and experiences they have in the world. (Merriam, 2009, p. 13) The researcher used classroom ethnography as qualitative research design. Classroom ethnography provides range of tools to delineate social norms existing in language classrooms. (Bloome and Green, 2012).

Semi-Structured Interviews and Observation:

The researcher used interviews to gather the information needed for this study. As widerberg stated, interviews is the preferred method when one wants to explore people's understanding of different phenomena (2002, p. 17). The researcher wants to explore student's understanding of gender discrimination and how does it shape their identity in a classroom. The researcher has chosen In-depth interviews to take, semi-structured to be precise for the study. It is easier to ask for authentic knowledge from students directly about the classroom experiences which shapes their perception of themselves. Also, to know the amount of sexism/ gender biases present in teachers' talk, the frequency of those words uttered out in the class and its impact on the students. The interviews are followed by an interview guide. That means the direction of the questions were given to the interviewee. The follow-up questions were also asked as they are crucial to clear out the doubts of the interviewee. (Hesse-Biber, 2007).

For the Observation of the teachers, researcher used convenient sampling to select the teachers to observe. Four different teachers from different departments of social sciences were taken into consideration. The observation tool was adopted to observe the teacher's talk systematically and to keep the record of all the gendered words uttered by the teachers or maybe not, their frequency and their impact on the students' perceptions which ultimately hinder them in performing well academically in classroom.

Population & Sampling:

Four social science departments from the Public University of Pakistan were used by the researcher. The departments are Sociology, Gender Studies, English, and International Relations. Students in their final year from each of the departments specified are the population for this study. The researcher selected a specific group of participants to observe how gender-biased language affected them in the classroom and shaped their self-perceptions at the university level.

Eight students were chosen for semi-structured interviews for this study. There are two participants—one male and one female—from each department. The interviews were conducted face-to-face at a variety of campus locations at the convenience of the participants, and each student had a time slot of 15-20 minutes.

Ethical consideration:

The director of the University of the Punjab's Institute of Applied and Clinical Psychology, Prof. Dr. Rukhsana Kausar, has created HEC-approved ethical guidelines, which the researcher has chosen to abide by in terms of ethical considerations. The guidelines include participant's consent, confidentiality and respecting the interviewee's integrity. The respondents were asked about their ethical concerns prior to gathering data on the topic. Their private information, such as name, location, etc., wouldn't be shared. The recorded information from the interviews would not be disclosed or used in any other way, as far as that was concerned. Everything was also recorded with a respondent's permission and consent. On the other hand, teachers' qualitative observations were also conducted with their consent.

Data Collection Procedure & Analysis:

The participants were asked a few semi-structured questions about gender, gender norms, culture, offensive words, phrases, metaphors, and proverbs, as well as their opinions of themselves. Each participant had a 15-20 minute time slot, and the data was collected using a voice recorder with their consent. The data was then thematically evaluated. Following a thematic analysis, major themes were extracted from the unstructured raw material and examined to provide the results.

The interviews were recorded and written down. The researcher did her best not to change the meaning of any recorded response while transcribing the data. Through the use of inductive coding, responses were examined.

Findings and Discussion

In order to address the two research questions—namely, 1- Gendered words and 2- how sexist language used by teachers in the classroom is affecting students' perceptions of themselves—the researcher employed an interviewing technique. The key conclusions from an interview are listed below.

1. Stereotypes affecting Identity

To begin with the Interview guide, researcher first asked students to answer whether they know about gender bias or sexism or not? The question was “Are you familiar with the words like sexism, gender bias or stereotypes?”

On response to the question, 7 out of 8 students answered yes.

Sexism or gender bias means when people of a particular gender are treated discriminatory. Gender stereotypes are the misconceptions or common beliefs about the people of a particular gender e.g. women can't drive, men are emotionally strong, and girls like pink color etc.

Participant-H. Gender is repeatedly created in an EFL classroom by enforcing masculine traits to the male and feminine traits to the female student. Hence, gender is not static but created again and again. Butler, (1988). Two female students said that teachers frequently criticize their career choices, saying that girls should study the humanities rather than logic, math, or international relations. Due to the fact that they must eventually get married and raise kids. They will have more success in the arts because they are already adept at keeping the class notebooks organized. Due to such gender distinction in the classroom discourse, it can be concluded that women are being stereotyped and such experiences shape the perceptions of themselves and the world around them. It can also be concluded that women are taught to stick to such gender discrimination. (Fuchs Epstein, 1986).

Two out of four male students also mentioned that they have faced sexism in the class in the shape of stereotypes. Participant C indicated during the interview that it was the day of our presentations and that the teacher had assigned the numbers by which we would be summoned to appear. The last group was mine, and there were four boys in it. We were abruptly invited to present in front of the class. We were all quite anxious, and we didn't understand why the teacher had called us first when we had been called last. The teacher's constant assumption is that the pupils at the back, particularly the boys, do no study at all. The majority of individuals would concur that these presumptions are mostly inaccurate nowadays, despite the fact that the language frequently supports the stereotypes. (Nneka, 2012). Not only sexist language stereotypes women but also shows how language can serve the purpose of deprecating women or

silence them as interactants. These sexist behaviors or attitudes shows denigrating one sex to the exaltation of the other. (Ivy and Baklund, 2012)

2. Gendered words used in an Instruction

Participants were asked questions about how normally a teacher addresses the class in order to determine whether the teacher used any specifically gendered language in their talk. On a response to this, three students mentioned that the teacher usually talk in regional language and say 'putr , baba, beta'. Instructor never says 'dhee, or amar'. The results of this study support Todd-Mancillas' (1981) observations that the common and everyday use of words ending in "he," "he," or "his" results in gender-biased evaluations.

One student also mentioned that teacher uses gender-neutral words like "listen everyone", "students" or "pay attention" when they want us to listen to them but typically with "guys" or "boys and girls" to collectively address our class.

The use of pronouns is a classic example of sexist discourse. In English, sexism is the practice of ignoring women by allowing masculine phrases to be used both specifically to refer to males and generically to refer to all humans.

Typically, terms denoting male sex are placed in front of words denoting female sex. Wilson, it is reported, contended in 1553 that it was more natural to put man before woman, as in male and female, husband and wife, father and mother, brother and sister, son and daughter, he and she, he or she, host and hostess, king and queen. The concept that males come first in the natural order is implicit in his insistence that males take precedence, and this is one of the first examples of a male arguing for not only male dominance but for this superiority to be represented in the form of language.

3. Teacher Judging Academic Capabilities

Students' abilities whether boys or girls is being judged by the teacher in a classroom. Teachers assume student's capabilities on the basis of their look, how do they look, what do they do, the way they choose something and why they choose it. For example, teacher judging male students on the basis of where do they sit in the class. If they sit at the back, teacher assumes that they do not study while teacher forgets about learning styles of students. Mostly kinesthetic students sit back in the class. A learning pedagogy known as kinesthetic learning by doing (Beget et al., 2004) enables students to interact with learning objects and practically learn by doing in a classroom setting. so, If teacher prefers a lecture method only. Kinesthetic learners prefers siting at back. Also, in another response a male participant stated that "teacher judged me on basis of how poorly I gave presentation in a class". Teacher assigned numbers to each group. In accordance to the numbers, everyone has to perform but she called our (boys group) first. Though ours was last and we sit at last. She scolded later. On other hand most of the female students reported that they were being judged on the basis of their looks/makeup they wear. One of the participant mentioned, once I and my other female friends were late in the class, teacher commented "you must be late because you took longer in getting ready for the class" while on other hand, she is the same teacher who never says a word to male students whenever they are late. Also other female participant stated teacher said, you should be in modeling the way you dress, it is not appropriate for the class. This class is not suitable for you. Study of Andrus , Jacobs, & Kurtoff (2018) concludes, women receive more comments on appearance than their academic capabilities. They receive less attention in the class than male students.

Other teacher commented on female participants as duffers and male as superiors. Teacher assigning field work to male participants and later ask them to teach girls is one of the example for it. Male participants experiencing linguistic sexism the same way as female participants do. Some stated that teacher underestimating their academic capabilities by giving first chance to speak to female students in class.

4. Promoting Sexist Jokes

Male and female participants equally faced sexist jokes in the class. Teachers usually putting sexist jokes towards girls as, they have to be at home at last. Why do they even burden themselves with so much studies or they have to get married at last to start household life with children. Jokes about their appearance as well. Even when male students are being joked about they are being done on their femininity. As one of the participant stated that teacher once called him as "Ms xyz" and laughed. Not only the teacher but everyone in the class laughed. It created deep impact on my

personality that I started to avoid participating in the class and become so demotivated.

also those males who chitchat in the class are being labelled and stereotypes as girls. Teacher of the opinion that girls do the chitchat not boys.

Teachers promoting femininity as bad cause them think that it is bad. According to Sunderland, females are typically more comfortable playing the role of boys than boys, and it would be quite uncomfortable for a boy to play the part of a girl (2000, p. 168) She notes, however, that while this may seem to indicate that girls are more free to act as they choose, it can equally be taken as guys believing that femininity is undesirable or inferior (Sunderland, 2000, p. 168). In light of this, it is crucial that educators examine these behaviours and foster dialogue about the issues associated with undermining others.

On other hand, a female participant stated that male joking with teachers do not always make them demotivate in the class but sometimes motivated to do that. When teacher jokes with male students, most of them do not even mind as it leads to frankness with a teacher. In result, they enjoy the favors like getting good marks, direct talking to the teacher. Not this benefits them but also the peers who are connected to them. This creates the chain of promoting sexist jokes in the class. Teachers also joke about how female students are not good at Maths and logic.

5. Impact of teacher's talk on student in class

Students of either gender mentioned that when teacher is positive and welcoming, they participate more. Nonsexist classrooms create domino effect. Students will feel included and confident hence they will participate more. Students of both the genders mentioned that they participate more and feel comfortable because of teacher's attitudes towards them. When teacher appreciate more, use gender inclusive language and pays attention to the opinions of the students. One of the female participant mentioned that she participates more when felt heard. If teacher is biased to either gender, I do not simply attend that class and become invisible. Amini & Birrandi (2012), Women frequently experience discrimination in language or content, which tends to limit their behavioral, linguistic and social roles.

Negative impact of teachers' talk has a profound impact on student's overall identity and personality. Most of the students responded in an interview that they negative impact of teacher's talk make them question their own identity. For instance, while one of the male students mentioned that teacher gave preference to the female students made me felt less competent than her. On the other hand, female participant also responded, if teacher is not encouraging and say mean words like, there was an experience where I wanted to perform in the class after the best student, and Teacher taunted me and said, "Now you would like to compete Mr. Xyz".

It is evident that both male and female students face similar educational experience, yet female students are marginalized more by teachers in the classroom. Teacher has deeper impact in modeling gender in the classroom. It has potential to regulate social norms by internalizing them within classroom. It was hypothesized in Bigler's developmental model (2005) that women would be more likely to receive gender discrimination in situations like STEM field.

6. Discrimination against either gender

Many earlier studies suggest that gendered classroom interaction could obstruct and even harm knowledge acquisition for males and females (Yepes, 1994), a little is known about how teacher's gender might affect teacher student interaction (Good et al, 1973). Duffy et al, (2001) concludes the tendency to interact more with male than female students, besides other factors, also depends on the academic subject being taught. It infers that teachers hold higher expectations of males.

In a result female students feel excluded sometimes in the classroom when they know teacher possess higher expectations of males on the basis of their perceptions of them. Study conducted by Salata (1994) reporting two thirds of silent students in large classrooms are females, not having any interaction or whatsoever with their professors. Gender biasness of the teachers is the reason that female students become silent and do not participate much in the class. And the students who do not interact with teachers are less likely to receive encouragement, chance to talk and hence

learn.- a threat recognized by Sternglanz and Luberger-Ficek (1977). Morrow (1979) argues even if volunteering is the cause, it is the teacher's responsibility to manage classroom interaction and provide equal opportunities for all students in classroom.

Male students also stated that they feel discriminated when teachers speak in a polite tone with the female students and asking their preferences on some topic or any ongoing class activity. One of the participants stated, teacher particularly asked a female student in a class, "do you want to answer this question: while the teacher never asked in such a way from male students. Also special treatment is given to the female students like no punishment at all.

Observation was carried out by the researcher to answer the research question no.1 i.e what are the sexist words being used by the teacher in a classroom. Following are the main findings from the data.

1. Gendered words used in a classroom

Teacher used 'he' pronoun when referring to both the genders in the classroom but teacher specifically used 'he' to the male participant when he had to praise. On other hand, they used femininity to demean a male student in class. "Boys who make tiktoks should be labelled as girls because of the way they dance..."

It was noticed that teacher used gendered pronouns in the medium of instruction which made students feel exclusive in the class. Teachers also used stereotypes and sexist jokes which emphasized on the gender norms to be followed.

Conclusion

Linguistic sexism does not only affect the perceptions of identity of the students but it also lead them to accept them as part of themselves. It makes them believe that some masculine/feminine characteristics are to be followed which ultimately make the gender norms. Hence, gender norms become the reality for them. If students want to achieve something different like girls in IT field or boys in arts, gender norms will hinder them in achieving them.

Both male and female students' conceptions of identity are influenced by teachers' words. Teachers must maintain social reforms since they are crucial to the greater effort to counter prevailing discourses (such as gender differentiation) that inevitably develop into grand narrative. Teachers do not only have to use less-gendered words but also encourage their students to use them. Teachers can implement strategies which could help both male and female genders to believe in themselves and learn effectively in the class irrespective of their gender. As It may have some degree of agency to alter its circumstances.

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References

- [1] Andrus, S., Charlotte, J., & Kuriloff, P. (2018). Miles to go: the continuing quest for gender equity in the classroom. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 100(2), 46-50.
- [2] Jones, M.G. (1989). Gender differences in teacher-students interactions. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 49, 33-38.
- [3] Merrett, F., & Wheldall, K. (1992). Teachers' use of praise and reprimands to boys and girls. *Educational Review*, 44(1), 73-84.

- [4] Sadker, M., Sadker, D., & Klein, S. (1991). Chapter 7: The issue of gender in elementary and secondary education. *Review of Research in Education*, 17, 269-334.
- [5] Berryman, Cynthia L., & James R. Wilcox. (1980). Attitudes toward male and female speech: Experiments on the effects of sex-typical language. *Western Journal of Speech Communication: WJSC*, 44(1), 50-59.
- [6] Faulstich-Wieland, H. (2000). *Individuum und gesellschaft. sozialisations-theorien und sozialisationsforschung* [Individual and society: Socialization theories and socialization research]. Munich, Germany: Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag.
- [7] Blumer, Herbert. (1969). *Symbolic interactionism: Perspective and method*. University of California Press.
- [8] Fuchs Epstein, Cynthia. (1986). Symbolic segregation: Similarities in the segregation and differences of the language and nonverbal communication of women and men. *Sociological Forum*, 1(1), 27-49.
- [9] Houtte, Mieke Van. (2004). Gender context of the school and study culture, or How the presence of girls affects the achievement of boys. *Educational Studies*, 30(4), 409-423.
- [10] Selvan, Saravuna R., & R. Suguna. (2013). Male chauvinistic language – A tool for suppressing women. *Language in India*, 13(9), 419-423.
- [11] Vejar, Cynthia. (2019). Symbolic interactionism. *Salem Press Encyclopedia*, 8.
- [12] Jeon, Y.H. (2004). The application of grounded theory and symbolic interactionism. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 18(3), 249-256,
- [13] Francis, Becky. (2002) Is the future really female? The impact and implications of gender for 14-16 year olds' career choices. *Journal of Education and Work*, 15(1), 75-88.
- [14] Marshall, C., & Reinhartz, J. (1997). Gender issues in the classroom. *The Clearing House*, 70(6), 33-337.
- [15] Brown, C.S., & C. Leaper. (2008). Perceived experiences with sexism among adolescent girls *Child Development*, 79(3), 685-704.

